

INFLUENCE OF SELF-AWARENESS ON JOB PERFORMANCE OF BUSINESS EDUCATORS IN FEDERAL UNIVERSITIES, SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: The study evaluated the influence of self-awareness on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. The specific objectives include to: assess the influence of self-confidence, realistic self-assessment and self-depreciating sense of humour on business educators' job performance in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design was used. The study adopted simple random sampling technique. The population of the study was 92 staff of business educators in the Federal universities under study. The whole population was used due to small number. 79 of the respondents returned the questionnaire accurately filled, which gave 89 percent response rate. Data were presented and analyzed using mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using regression. The findings indicated that all the variables have a positive significant influence on business educators job performance in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria. With this result we can concluded that the more self-aware business educators are, the more their productivity and performance will improve. Specifically, the more business educators possess self-awareness competencies the more likely their output will be for their institutions. Based on the above facts, we recommend that; management of higher institutions should create more awareness about the importance of self-confidence to their business educators.

Keywords: Self-awareness, Job Performance, Business Educators, Self-confidence, Realistic Self-assessment, Self-depreciating Sense of Humour.

1.1 Introduction

Self-awareness is a vital element of emotional intelligence that helps employees, managers and leaders to recognise and regulate emotions, personal strengths and weaknesses. Emotional intelligence (EI) has become a very important topic in management and education in the last decade, especially in regard to how it affects today's employees, managers and leaders. In recent times, employers have incorporated emotional intelligence tests in their interviews, perhaps on the assumption that, those high in emotional intelligence would make better employees, leaders and co-workers (Cherry, 2018). Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to perceive, control, and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be earned and strengthened, while others claim it is an inborn characteristic. It can also be described as the capacity to act from receptivity rather than react impulsively and thoughtlessly by using your awareness and sensitivity to identify the feelings that underlie interpersonal communication. Additionally, it is believed that having a high level of emotional intelligence can help one succeed in their career, lead and inspire others, and negotiate the

social complexities of the workplace. Indeed, many companies now use emotional quotient (EQ) testing prior to hiring, rating emotional intelligence as highly as technical abilities when evaluating potential candidates. According to Scuderi (2014) in any human endeavour which includes working in organisation, people or employees that are believed to be highly intelligent may not succeed or perform better than those who are believed to be less intelligent. The difference between the effectiveness and efficiency in performances may be hinged on abilities, which according to Scuderi (2014) may be as a result of employee's emotions.

Emotions, according to Salovey *et al.* (2007) are organised responses crossing the physiological, cognitive, motivational and exponential sub-systems of the brain. Goleman (2005) defined emotions as guiding forces that help humans in facing predicaments and tasks that one's intelligence alone cannot handle. The author went further to state that, for better or worse, intelligence can come to nothing when emotion holds sway; that is, when employee's emotional states such as anger, anxiety, depression, sorrow, excitement among others control or determine the employee's job performance. In other words, employees need to act based on their emotional intelligence. This will guide their actions, inactions and reactions to situations and people, thereby leading to self-awareness.

Self-awareness is the ability to recognise and understand personal moods and emotions and drives, as well as their effect on others (Mohamad and Jais, 2015). It consists of self-confidence, realistic self-assessment and a self-depreciating sense of humour. Self-awareness depends on one's ability to monitor one's own emotional state and to correctly identify and name one's emotions (Gontur and Dekom, 2017). According to Goleman *et al.* (2002) self-awareness means having a deep understanding of one's emotions, as well as strengths, limitations and one's values and motives. The scholars stressed that people with strong self-awareness are realistic. They are not overly self-critical or naively hopeful. Goleman *et al.* (2002) further stated that self-aware leaders, managers and employees understand their values, goals, passions and drives and are always willing to put in their best to ensure that organisational goals and objectives are achieved.

According to Efi *et al.* (2018), the role of education as an instrument for promoting the socio-economic, political and cultural development of any nation can never be over-emphasized. It is worthy of note that this role is also anchored by business educators. Business educators who have self-awareness skills would become aware of how to exploit or make full use of their strengths by concentrating on courses they can handle very well and play down on their weaknesses by refusing to accept to take or handle courses outside their areas of competence. It would also help them to become aware of their drives, values and limitations in order to develop self-confidence in their duties. Self-awareness skill would help business educators to know that all students do not have the same intelligent quotients; some learn at a slow pace while others learn at a fast pace, as such strategies need to be put in place to carry everyone along. This would help business educators to develop self-regulation skill to subsequently handle delicate situations geared towards attainment of educational and personal goals and objectives.

Several studies conducted in the advance world of America, Europe, and in some parts of Asia have shown that self-awareness as a part of emotional intelligence leads to job performance. However, despite these great successes recorded in these parts of the world on the usefulness of this crucial aspect of emotional intelligence, there is very little evidence to show that such studies have been carried out in Nigeria, especially among

business educators in Federal Universities, south-south Nigerian. Furthermore, its also been observed that some business educators could not regulate or control their emotions or negative impulses especially when dealing with some difficult, stubborn, dull and recalcitrant students as well as with some unfriendly, egoistic, high-handed and domineering co-workers and leaders, which may be as a result of lack of self-awareness skills which is part of emotional intelligence. This may pose adverse or negative impacts on their job performance. As such, this study sought to bridge the gap in the literature by assessing the influence of self-awareness on business educators' job performance in Federal Universities, South-South, Nigeria.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to examine the influence of self-awareness on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. The specific objectives include to:

- i. assess the influence of self-confidence on business educators' job performance in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria;
- ii. examine the impact of realistic self-assessment on business educators' job performance in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria;
- iii. assess the influence of self-depreciating sense of humour on business educators' job performance in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria.

1.3 Research Questions

- i. How does self-confidence influence job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria
- ii. How does realistic self-assessment impact job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria
- iii. How does self-depreciating sense of humour influence job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

1.4 Hypotheses of the Study

H₀₁: Self-confidence does not influence job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

H₀₂: Realistic self-assessment does not impact job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

H₀₃: Self-depreciating sense of humour does not influence job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Concept of Self-awareness

Self-awareness can be viewed as the ability to recognise and understand one's own emotions (Cherry, 2018b). It is the foundational building block of emotional intelligence, since regulating ourselves, having empathy for others and so on all rely on identifying and understanding emotions in ourselves. Cherry (2018a) defined self-awareness as the capacity to recognise and understand emotions and to have sense of how one's actions, moods and the emotions of others take effect. It involves keeping track of emotion and noticing different emotional reactions, as well as being able to identify the emotions correctly. Self-awareness also includes recognising that

how we feel and what we do are related, and having awareness of one's own personal strengths and limitations (Cherry, 2018a). It is associated with being open to different experiences and new ideas and learning from social interactions.

Houston (2019) viewed self-awareness as the ability to recognise and understand one's own emotions and their impact on others. It is the first step toward introspective self-evaluation and enables one to identify behavioural and emotional aspects of one's psychological make-up which one can then target for change. Emotional self-awareness is also about recognising what motivates one and in turn what brings one fulfilment (Houston, 2019). Many studies have since shown that Emotional Intelligence, especially the self-awareness domain may, in fact, predict and account for a broad range of human behaviours among them; mental and physical health, life-satisfaction/self-reported and well-being, positive social interactions, academic achievements and workplace performance (Raz and Zysberg, 2014). Psychologists, educationists, managers, leaders and researchers continue this trend even to this day through their various research and workplace applications. Goleman's (1995) initial published research surmised that up to 67 percent of all competencies that were deemed essential for high performers were actually related to self-awareness domain of emotional intelligence.

Self-awareness means being aware of what one is feeling moment to moment as well as seeking to understand the impact this has on others (Raz and Zysberg, 2014). Self-awareness is at the core of everything. It describes one's ability to not only understand one's strengths and weaknesses, but to recognise one's emotions and the effect they have on one and one's team performance (Landry, 2019). According to research by organisational psychologist, Eurich cited in Landry (2019), 95 percent of people think they are self-aware, but only 10 to 15 percent actually are, and that can pose serious problems for employees. Working with colleagues who are not self-aware can cut a team success into half, and lead to increased stress and decreased motivation. Landry (2019) stressed that, in order to bring out the best in others, one first need to bring out the best in oneself, which is where self-awareness comes into play. One easy way to assess one's self-awareness is by completing 360-degree feedback in which one evaluates one's performance and then match it up against the opinions of one's boss, peers and direct reports. Through this process, one would gain insights into one's own behaviour and discover how one is perceived in the organisation.

2.1.1 Importance of Self-awareness to Employees

Self-awareness has numerous benefits to employees. According to Forsey (2018), these benefits includes:

- i. improves skills by recognising what one does well and what one needs to improve;
- ii. raises happiness levels by aligning one's ideals with one's actions;
- iii. becomes a better leader by understanding how employees perceive one's behaviour;
- iv. strengthens work and personal relationships by managing emotions;
- v. increases work motivation by seeking out one's true passions and
- vi. decreases stress by identifying emotions and lessening tasks one does not enjoy.

2.1.2 Components of Self-awareness

Self-confidence is possessing the belief in oneself to be able to handle most situations in life, organizations and relationship with others. Beyond merely being a happy emotion, confidence is an attitude and way of living that opens doors to opportunity, drive, and success. It all comes down to being authentic. You will believe you can

succeed when you have confidence. It empowers you to face challenges head-on and overcome obstacles head-on. Taking on new challenges with excitement is a sign of confidence in the workplace. A lack of confidence in yourself will prevent you from succeeding. Why should others believe in you if you do not believe in yourself? People are fed by confidence; if you show them that you believe, they will believe as well. If you have confidence in yourself, you will not give up when you make mistakes and encounter difficulties. You experiment and learn new techniques, confident that you will overcome the challenge in due course. If you are insecure, you may end up being wrong. When you are self-assured, you view obstacles as opportunities for growth and development rather than reasons to give up.

It is pertinent to note that confidence fluctuates, and in some circumstances and moments, you might feel more confident than in others. You will have greater access to confidence when faced with challenges if you focus on increasing it in any given area. Finding out what gives you more confidence in some circumstances than others is crucial. Recognize and acknowledge the ways in which you act, speak, and behave when you are in a confident situation, and then apply these strategies to less confident ones.

Realistic self-assessment is an assessment which allows an individual or an employee to assess their own performance. It is the process of observing oneself in order to assess facets that are important to one's identity. It is seen as one of the motives that drive self-evaluation, along with self-verification and self-enhancement. Sedikides (1993) opine that self-assessment motive will prompt people to seek information to confirm their ambiguous self-concept rather than their convinced self-concept and at the same time people use self-assessment to improve their certainty of their own self-knowledge. It can be very valuable in helping an employee develop self-reflection. Depreciating sense of humour is a form of self-awareness, but the person using that humour may only point out what they feel are negative things or things they do not like about themselves, but says it aloud in a funny or joking way.

2.1.3 Job performance

Job performance (sometimes also called work performance) is a widely used tool and metric in management, however, organisations rarely address what it really is, which dimension it includes, and in which area of work it becomes important. Kasemsap (2017) viewed job performance as the accomplishment of a given task measured against the standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. It refers to the ability of workers to perform their jobs well (Ahmad, 2011). It is also described as work-related activities expected of an employee and how well those activities are executed. Kankaew and Treruttanaset (2021) defined job performance as the performance which is composed of quantity and quality of work, timeliness, economics and the result of the work. It relates to how individuals perform in their job duties in terms of expected quantity and quality of jobs and it has been defined as the overall expected value from employee's behaviour carried out over the course of a set period of time (Turanligil and Farooq, 2019).

Job performance relates to how individuals perform in their assigned duties. In addition to training and natural ability (like dexterity or an inherent skill with numbers, job performance is impacted by workplace environment factors including physically demanding tasks, employees' morale, stress levels and working extended hours. Poor conditions and high stress can lead to compromising health habits like smoking and or poor diet, which then have increasing detrimental effects on job performance. On the other end of the spectrum, well designed

work environments, low stress and a supportive employer can greatly increase job performance. Job performance is an important part of workplace productivity and safety.

According to Martocchio (2015) job performance is the total expected value to the organisation of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a standard or specified period of time. Martocchio (2015) emphasized two key issues in this definition. First, performance is an aggregated property of multiple, discrete behaviour that occur overtime. Second, the property of behaviour to which performance refers is its expected value to the organisation. Jacobs *et al.* (2013) opined that job performance relates to the act of doing a job. It is a means to reach a goal or set of goals within a job, role or organisation, but not the actual consequences of the acts performed with a job (Jacob *et al.*, 2013). The scholars affirmed that job performance is not a single action but rather a “complex activity”. Performance in a job is strictly a behaviour and a separate entity from the outcomes of a particular job which relate to success and productivity.

2.1.4 Self-awareness and Job Performance

Self-awareness is the ability to notice feelings, physical sensations, reactions, habits, behaviours and thoughts (Warley, 2017). It involves monitoring one’s stress, thoughts, emotions and beliefs (Davis, 2019). It is important because it is a major mechanism influencing personal development. High self-awareness is a social predictor of good success in life, perhaps because self-aware people know when an opportunity is a good fit for them and how to make an appropriate enterprise work well (Davis, 2019). The importance of self-awareness goes beyond well-being and mental health to include substantial impacts on day-to-day activities. It has important effects on job performance with reflection and mindfulness encouraging persistence with tasks despite performance related stress (Feldman *et al.*, 2014) and rumination related to interpersonal difficulties (Brinker *et al.*, 2014)

Self-awareness is an individual’s ability to appreciate the strengths and weaknesses of one’s own character (Srivastava, 2015). Realising this will enable one to take actions and make choices and decisions that are consistent with one’s abilities. Research shows that self-awareness is directly related to both emotional intelligence and success (Srivastava, 2015). Srivastava, pointed out that self-awareness helps employees create achievable goals because they can consider their strengths, weaknesses, and what drives them when they are setting goals. It allows them to guide themselves down the right path by choosing to pursue the opportunities that best fit their skills set, preferences and tendencies. It makes it easier to identify situations and people that hit our triggers and enables us to anticipate our own reactions. It allows employees and leaders to make positive behavioural changes that can lead to greater personal and interpersonal success (Srivastava, 2015). Self-awareness recognises the importance of one’s own feelings and how it affects one’s strengths and weaknesses (Shalzadet *al.*, 2011). Self-awareness can be seen as important element that influences job performance (Hua, 2017). Individuals with accurate self-awareness know their emotions properly. Self-awareness skills assist employees to seek for feedback and learn from their past mistakes and identify where they need to work on when they work with others in teams who have an edge over them. (Shalzadet *al.*, 2011).

Self-awareness is the key to personal growth. Without accurate information regarding their strengths and weaknesses, employees will really fool themselves. They will mess up projects, relationships and even life plans. Knowing their strengths and weaknesses is the best way to really know themselves (Nuckolls, 2018).

Self-awareness skill is very important for employees because when they have a better understanding of themselves, they will see themselves as unique and separate individuals. They will then be empowered to make changes and to build on their areas of strength as well as identify areas where they would like to make improvements (Hackston, 2019). Self-awareness is being conscious of what one is good at while acknowledging what one still has yet to learn. This includes admitting when one does not have the answer and owning up to mistakes (Devonish, 2016). Self-awareness has become increasingly important to job performance and research has shown that people with a more accurate self-perception tend to perform better in the workplace (Hackston, 2019; Hua, 2017; Gontur and Dekom, 2017).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Ability Theory of Emotional Intelligence

Ability theory of Emotional Intelligence (EI) was developed by Peter Salovey and John Mayer in 1990. The theorists originally conceptualised Emotional intelligence as encompassing three types of mental processes; appraisal and expression of emotions and the utilisation of emotions. However, Salovey and Mayer's research over several years has allowed them to modify and re-define their conceptualisation or categorisation of EI. The theorists currently posit or assert that, EI includes four types of abilities:

- a. perceiving emotions: the ability to detect and decipher emotions in faces, pictures, voices and cultural artifacts including the ability to identify one's own emotions. Perceiving emotions represent a basic aspect of emotional intelligence as it makes all other processing of emotional information possible.
- b. using emotions: the ability to harness emotions to facilitate various cognitive activities, such as thinking and problem-solving. The emotionally intelligent person can capitalise fully upon his or her changing moods in order to best fit the task at hand.
- c. understanding emotions: the ability to comprehend emotion language and to appreciate complicated relationships among emotions. For example, understanding emotions encompasses the ability to be sensitive to slight variations between emotions, and the ability to recognise and describe how emotions evolve over time.
- d. managing emotions: the ability to regulate emotions in both ourselves and in others. Therefore, the emotionally intelligent person can harness emotions, even negative ones and manage them to achieve intended goals.

The ability-based theory views emotions as useful sources of information that help one to make sense of and navigate the social environment. The theory proposes that individuals vary in their ability to process information of an emotional nature and in their ability to relate emotional processing to a wider cognition. This ability is seen to manifest itself in certain adaptive behaviours. The relevance of this theory to the present study is that, business educators who have high EI skills would be able to identify, detect and decipher their emotions, that of their colleagues and students, express emotions accurately and also manage their emotions appropriately. This ability would in no small measure lead to their improved job performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

Okpara and Edwin (2015) conducted a study on self-awareness and organisational performance in the Nigerian banking sector. The purpose of the study was to investigate the relationship between self-awareness and organisational performance in the Nigerian banking industry. The study was a survey and the sample consisted

of two hundred and ten (210) bank managers in South-South Zone, Nigeria. Data were collected mainly in cities with high concentration of the banks through interview and questionnaire instrument found to be reliable with Cronbach alpha values of 0.7 and above. Four hypotheses were formulated and tested using the Spearman Rank Correlation Co-efficient with the aid of statistical package for social science. The results of the analysis at .05 level of significance showed that self-awareness is positively related to net profit and return on investment, but no strong relationship was found between self-awareness and market share. The interview results also supported the findings. Based on the results, it was concluded that self-awareness positively influences net profit and return on investment. This study investigated the relationship between self-awareness and performance in the banking sector while the current study is concerned with business educators.

Marembo and Chinyamurindi (2018) conducted a study on the influence of demographic variables on emotional intelligence among early career academics (ECAs) in South Africa. The quantitative approach was followed in conducting the study. Data were collected from a sample of 220 ECAs in a selected University in South Africa. A self-administered questionnaire was sent to the participants using survey monkey online data collection tool. Emotional intelligence was measured using the Schutte Emotional Intelligence Scale. The findings revealed a significant EI level differences based on the participants' ethnic background. However, no significant differences in EI levels could be found based on the respondents' gender, age and work experience. Although this study was conducted in the educational sector, the choice of variables differs from the current study.

Ayogu (2015) carried out a study on emotional intelligence and implication for career development in selected Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria. The study sought to assess the significant areas that require emotional intelligence in the management of selected Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria; assess the implication of emotional intelligence on the non-academic staff; ascertain the attributes of emotional intelligence on the non-academic staff, ascertain the attributes of emotional intelligence that enhance academic staff career development; determine the extent of the relationship between motivation and training and examine the extent to which emotional intelligence affects career development in selected Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria. The study adopted the survey research design and data were collected from primary source through questionnaire and oral interview. Data were also obtained from secondary sources. The target population of the study comprised both academic and non-academic staff of Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria. A sample size of six hundred and fifty-one (651) respondents was determined using the finite population formula of Godden (2004). The chi-square statistics, z-test, linear regression and the pearson product moment correlation co-efficient through the application of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS 17.0 windows) were used to test the hypotheses stated. The findings indicated that leadership, negotiation and decision making are significant areas that require emotional intelligence in the management of selected Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria. The relationship between Ayogu's (2015) work and the present study is motivation; one of the EI variables. The impact of EI on academic staff job performance is also a serious link. The past and the present study also adopted survey research design but the current study was conducted in south-south Nigeria.

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted survey research design. This design was used since it aided the researcher to collect data directly from the respondents. Population of the study consisted of 92 Business Educators in the five Federal Universities in South-South, Nigeria (Staff Nominal Roll of the five Federal Universities in the 2020/2021 academic session).

Table 1: Distribution of the Study Population

S/N.	Name of Universities	Number of Business Educators	Male	Female
1.	University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State	11	7	4
2.	University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State	33	21	12
3.	University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State	6	5	1
4.	University of Benin, Edo State	30	20	10
5.	Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State	12	9	3
Total		92	61	31

Source: Staff Nominal Roll Per University (2024).

By this small number, the entire population was used as the sample. This was informed by the assertion that, when the population is small, studying the entire population will provide higher validity and better understanding of the relationship between the variables in the study. This is in line with Osuala (2005) who opined that the entire population should be studied when the population is relatively small.

Purposive sampling technique was adopted for this study. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire which was administered to the respondents in their respective offices. Scoring of the research instrument was done using Likert Scale. In the questionnaire, the respondents responded by indicating their degree of agreement or disagreement to each statement by ticking along the column provided. Scoring of the questionnaire was graded as follows: Strongly agree (SA) - 5; Agree (A) – 4; Undecided (UN) – 3; Disagree (D) – 2; Strongly disagree (SD) – 1.

The descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the study. The descriptive statistics were percentage and frequency distribution tables which were used to capture respondents' demographic characteristics and frequency distribution of the responses on the study variables. Inferential statistics was used to assess the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The simple linear regression analysis was the inferential statistics used. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22 was used to aid the analysis.

Based on the variables of this study, the simple linear regression equations are presented thus;

$$Jp = a1 + b1Sc + \dots e \quad \text{equation 1}$$

$$Jp = a2 + b2Sa + \dots e \quad \text{equation 2}$$

$$Jp = a3 + b3Sd + \dots e \quad \text{equation 3}$$

Where;

Jp (Y) = Job Performance

Sc (X1) = Self-confidence

Sa (X2) = Self-assessment

Sd (X3) = Self-depreciating

e = error term

a = constant

4.0 Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

Table 2: Summary of Questionnaire Administration and Collection

Questionnaire Administered	Collected	%
Total membership copies served	92	100
Total membership copies completed corrected	79	85.9
Total membership copies incorrectly filled	4	4.4
Total membership copies not returned	9	9.7

Source: Field Survey (2024)

As indicated in Table 2, a total of 92 copies of questionnaire were distributed, 79 copies representing 85.9% were returned in useable form to the researcher, 4 copies representing 4.4% were returned but not in useable form while a total of 9 copies were not returned. Consequently, since the number returned in useable form is higher than others, the response rate being greater than half, the researchers considered this response adequate representation of the sampled frame of the study. These 79 responses therefore represent 100% of the instrument used in subsequent analysis of this study. In order words, the analyses done in this study are based on the responses obtained from these 79 respondents.

Table 3: Research responses on Self Confidence

S/N	Self-confidence.	Strong Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (n) %
1	I have the ability to exhibit self confidence in all situation.	22 (27.8)	41 (51.9)	13 (16.5)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
2	Ability to realize self-values and beliefs	10 (12.7)	44 (55.7)	22 (27.8)	3 (3.8)	0 (0)	79 (100)
3	Ability to have a strong sense of self-worth and capabilities	28 (35.4)	33 (41.8)	5 (6.3)	8 (10.1)	5 (6.3)	79 (100)

Source: The Researcher's Compilation (2024).

Table 3 shows that 22(27.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have the ability to exhibit self-confidence in all situation; 41(51.9%) of the respondents also agree; 13(16.5%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 1(1.3%) of the respondents strongly disagree and disagree that they have the ability to exhibit self-confidence in all situation. For question 2, 10(12.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have ability to realise their self-values and beliefs. 44(55.7%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 22(27.8%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 3(3.8%) of the respondents disagree that they have ability to realise their self-values and beliefs. For question 3, 28(35.4) of the respondents strongly agree that they possess ability to have a strong sense of self-worth. 33(41.8%) agree, 5(6.3%) were

undecided, 8(10.1%) disagree while 5 (6.3%) respondents strongly disagree that they possess ability to have a strong sense of self-worth.

Table 4: Research responses on Realistic self-assessment

S/N	Self-assessment	Strong Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (n) %
1	Ability to understand and know self	19 (24.1)	37 (46.8)	20 (25.3)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
2	Ability to understand own feelings and what triggers them.	31 (31.2)	34 (43.0)	12 (15.2)	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
3	Ability to know own strengths and weaknesses	10 (12.7)	44 (55.7)	21 (26.6)	3 (3.8)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)

Source: The Researcher’s Compilation (2024).

Table 4 reveals that 19(24.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have the ability to understand and know themselves; 37(46.8%) of the respondents also agree; 20(25.3%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 1(1.3%) of the respondents strongly disagree and disagree that they have the ability to understand and know themselves. Question 2, 31(31.2%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have the ability to understand own feelings and what triggers them. 34(43.0%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 12(15.2%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 1(1.3%) of the respondents disagree while 1(1.3%) strongly disagree that they have the ability to understand own feelings and what triggers them. For question 3, 10(12.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that they possess ability to know own strengths and weaknesses. 44(55.7%) agree, 21(26.6%) were undecided, 3(3.8%) disagree while 1 (1.3%) respondent strongly disagree that they possess ability to know own strengths and weaknesses.

Table 5: Research responses on Self depreciating sense of humour

S/N	Self-depreciating	Strong Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (n) %
1	Ability to recognize feelings and their effects.	23 (29.1)	35 (44.3)	18 (22.8)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
2	Ability to use perception effectively	22 (27.8)	41 (51.9)	13 (16.5)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
3	Ability to know own habits	10 (12.7)	44 (55.7)	21 (26.6)	3 (3.8)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)

Source: The Researcher's Compilation (2024).

Table 5 indicates that 23(29.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have the ability to recognize feelings and their effects; 35(44.3%) of the respondents also agree; 18(22.8%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 1(1.3%) of the respondents strongly disagree that they have the ability to recognize feelings and their effects. For question 2, 22(27.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that they have ability to use perception effectively. 41(51.9%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 13(16.5%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 2(2.5%) of the respondents disagree while 1(1.3%) strongly disagree that they have ability to use perception effectively. For question 3, 10(12.7%) of the respondents strongly agree that they possess ability to know own habits. 44(55.7%) agree, 21(26.6%) were undecided, 3(3.8%) disagree while 1 (1.3%) respondent strongly disagree that they possess ability to know own habits.

Table 6: Research responses on Job performance

S/N	Job performance	Strong Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)	Total (n) %
1	I am very passionate about my work	23 (29.1)	35 (44.3)	17 (21.5)	2 (2.5)	2 (2.5)	79 (100)
2	I can handle multiple assignments for achieving organizational goals.	22 (27.8)	41 (51.9)	13 (16.5)	2 (2.5)	1 (1.3)	79 (100)
3	I am capable of handling my assignments without much supervision	33 (41.8)	30 (38.0)	4 (5.1)	6 (7.6)	6 (7.6)	79 (100)

Source: The Researcher's Compilation (2024).

Table 6 shows that 23(29.1%) of the respondents strongly agree that they very passionate about their work; 35(44.3%) of the respondents also agree; 17(21.5%) of the respondents were neutral; while 2(2.5%) of the respondents and 2(2.5%) of the respondents strongly disagree that they are very passionate about their work. For question 2, 22(27.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that they can handle multiple assignments for achieving organizational goals. 41(51.9%) of the respondents also agree with the statement; 13(16.5%) of the respondents were neutral. On the other hand, 2(2.5%) of the respondents disagree while 1(1.3%) strongly disagree that they can handle multiple assignments for achieving organizational goals. For question 3, 33(41.8%) of the respondents strongly agree that they are capable of handling their assignments without much supervision. 30(38.0%) agree, 4(5.1%) were undecided, 6(7.6%) disagree while 6(7.6%) respondents strongly disagree that they are capable of handling their assignments without much supervision

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

H01: Self-confidence does not influence job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.489 ^a	.239	.230	1.66572

a. Predictors: (Constant), SelfCon

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	67.239	1	67.239	24.234	.000 ^b
	Residual	213.647	77	2.775		
	Total	280.886	78			

a. Dependent Variable: Perf

b. Predictors: (Constant), SelfCon

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.675	1.291		4.396	.000
	SelfCon	.538	.109	.489	4.923	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Perf

The result of the regression analysis showed that the dependent variable was moderately correlated at R=0.489. The coefficient of determination $R^2=0.239$ and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2= 0.230$. Self-confidence explained 2.3% of variance of job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south Nigeria. From the anova table, the statistical significance of the regression model shows that $P < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05. This means that it is a good fit. In assessing the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Self-confidence showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.538$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$. This finding shows that every 1 unit change in self-confidence will lead to 0.53 change in job performance of business educators. However, since the $p\text{-value}=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that self-confidence have a significant influence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria.

H02: Realistic self-assessment does not impact job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.569 ^a	.324	.315	1.57036

a. Predictors: (Constant), SelfAss

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	91.001	1	91.001	36.902	.000 ^b
	Residual	189.885	77	2.466		
	Total	280.886	78			

a. Dependent Variable: Perf

b. Predictors: (Constant), SelfAss

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.248	1.445		2.247	.027
	SelfAss	.737	.121	.569	6.075	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Perf

The result of the regression analysis showed that the dependent variable was moderately correlated at $R=0.569$. The coefficient of determination $R^2=0.324$ and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2= 0.315$. Realistic self-assessment explained 3.1% of variance of job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south Nigeria. From the anova table, the statistical significance of the regression model shows that $P < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05. This means that it is a good fit. To assess the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Realistic self-assessment showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.737$, p -value=0.000. This finding shows that every 1 unit change in realistic self-assessment will lead to 0.73 change in job performance of business educators. However, since the p -value=0.000 which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that realistic self-assessment has a significant influence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria.

H03: Self-depreciating sense of humour does not influence job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.754 ^a	.569	.563	1.25399

a. Predictors: (Constant), SelfDep

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	159.804	1	159.804	101.624	.000 ^b
	Residual	121.082	77	1.572		
	Total	280.886	78			

a. Dependent Variable: Perf

b. Predictors: (Constant), SelfDep

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.670	1.129		.593	.555
SelfDep	.961	.095	.754	10.081	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Perf

The result of the regression analysis revealed that the dependent variable was strongly correlated at $R=0.754$. The coefficient of determination $R^2=0.569$ and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2= 0.563$. Self-depreciating sense of humour explained 5.6% of variance of job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south Nigeria. From the anova table, the statistical significance of the regression model shows that $P < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05. This means that it is a good fit. In order to assess the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Self-depreciating sense of humour showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.961$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$. This finding reveals that every 1unit change in self-depreciating sense of humour will lead to 0.96 change in job performance of business educators. However, since the $p\text{-value}=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that self-depreciating sense of humour have a significant influence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The first objective of the study was to assess the influence of self-confidence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. In line with this, it was the hypothesized that self-confidence does not influence job performance of business educators in federal universities. From the regression analysis, it showed that the dependent variable was moderately correlated at $R=0.489$. The coefficient of determination $R^2=0.239$ and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2= 0.230$. Self-confidence explained 2.3% of variance of job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south Nigeria. In assessing the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Self-confidence showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta=0.538$, $p\text{-value}=0.000$. This finding shows that every 1unit change in self-confidence will lead to 0.53 change in job performance of business educators. However, since the $p\text{-value}=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that self-confidence have a significant influence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Okpara and Edwin (2015). In their study, it was revealed that self-awareness influences net profit in the banking sector. Also, self-awareness as a part of emotional intelligence leads to effective and efficient organisational and employees' performance. This study though conducted in Nigeria concentrated on the banking sector while the current study is concerned in the educational sector in the south-south region of Nigeria.

The second objective was to examine the impact of realistic self-assessment on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. Result of the regression analysis showed that the dependent variable was moderately correlated at $R=0.569$. The coefficient of determination $R^2=0.324$ and the

adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2 = 0.315$. Realistic self-assessment explained 3.1% of variance of job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south Nigeria. To assess the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Realistic self-assessment showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta = 0.737$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$. This finding shows that every 1 unit change in realistic self-assessment will lead to 0.73 change in job performance of business educators. However, since the $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that realistic self-assessment has a significant influence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. This study was in agreement with the findings of Marembo and Chinyamurindi (2018). In their findings they found out that some demographic variables impact on emotional intelligence among early career academics (ECAs) in South Africa. This study was conducted in south Africa while the current study is conducted in Nigeria.

The third objective was to assess the influence of self-depreciating sense of humour on business educators' job performance in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. Regression analysis result showed that the dependent variable was strongly correlated at $R = 0.754$. The coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.569$ and the adjusted coefficient of determination; adjusted $R^2 = 0.563$. Self-depreciating sense of humour explained 5.6% of variance of job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south Nigeria. From the anova table, the statistical significance of the regression model shows that $P < 0.0005$, which is less than 0.05. This means that it is a good fit. In order to assess the relative importance of the dependent variable on the independent variable, beta coefficient is provided on the coefficient table. Self-depreciating sense of humour showed a significant standardized coefficient of $\beta = 0.961$, $p\text{-value} = 0.000$. This finding reveals that every 1 unit change in self-depreciating sense of humour will lead to 0.96 change in job performance of business educators. However, since the $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ which is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis. As a result, we conclude that self-depreciating sense of humour have a significant influence on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

The major objective this study was to assess the influence of self-awareness on job performance of business educators in federal universities, south-south, Nigeria. Self-awareness was decomposed to self-confidence, realistic self-assessment and self-depreciating sense of humour. Thus far, findings from the study reveals that all the variables have a positive significant influence on business educators' job performance in federal universities in south-south, Nigeria.

With this result we can conclude that the more self-aware business educators are, the more their productivity and performance will improve. Specifically, the more business educators possess self-awareness competencies the more likely their output will be for their institutions. Based on the above facts, we recommend that; management of higher institutions should create more awareness about the importance of self-confidence to their business educators. This may be in form of trainings or seminars on competencies of self-awareness. Also, business educators should be encouraged to by managements of higher institutions to always have a realistic self-assessment. This may aid them identify when they are doing well or otherwise. Even when they are doing well, there is still room for further improvement. Equally, the ability to quickly sense when one's sense of

humour is depreciating is a great trait to possess as this could help enhance self-awareness and in turn enhance greater performance. This, Management of universities in south-south Nigeria should endeavour to assess sense of humour when conducting the yearly appraisal via the employees' appraisal forms.

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